

ANALYSIS OF SPECTRAL MEASUREMENT METHODS

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Abstract: *At present, several dozens of analytical methods are used in analytical measurements in various industries and in scientific research. From the consideration of their classifications, as well as the growth trend in the volume of analytical instrumentation, one can single out the most widely used method in practice - the spectrometric method for measuring and analyzing substances with impurities. This article discusses the issue of choosing one of the spectral analysis methods for further processing of signals coming from spectrometric equipment.*

Keywords: *spectrometric analysis, x-ray diffraction analysis*

Spectral analysis is a physical method for the qualitative and quantitative determination of the atomic and molecular composition of a substance, based on the study of its spectra. The physical basis of spectral analysis is the spectroscopy of atoms and molecules, it is classified according to the purpose of the analysis and the types of spectra. Atomic spectral analysis determines the elemental composition of a sample from atomic (ionic) emission and absorption spectra, molecular spectral analysis determines the molecular composition of a substance from molecular absorption, luminescence and Raman spectra [1].

Emission spectral analysis is carried out according to the emission spectra of atoms, ions and molecules (optical and X-ray spectra) excited by various sources of electromagnetic radiation in the range from γ -radiation to microwave [2].

Absorption spectral analysis is carried out according to the absorption spectra of electromagnetic radiation by the analyzed objects (atoms, molecules, ions of a substance in various states of aggregation). The types of radiation on which the spectral analysis is based are listed in Table. 1.1.

Spectral analysis methods are extremely widely used in industry and ecology. At the same time, the methods of atomic emission spectral analysis are indispensable for determining trace amounts of heavy metals in water, air, and soil, while absorption spectroscopy is used to identify and establish the structure of organic compounds, organometallic compounds, and many inorganic gases. The production of spectrometers in the USA in absolute terms exceeds the production of any other instruments, which is evident from the dynamics of sales of spectrophotometers [3].

Table 1.1. - Characterization of spectral methods

Types of radiation	Characteristic photon energy λ , m	Detection threshold, %
Radio frequency (nuclear magnetic resonance, electron paramagnetic resonance)	10^1 - 10^{-1}	10^{-3}
Microwave	10^1 - 10^{-3}	10^{-2}
Optical UV	-	10^{-7}
Optical visible	10^{-6} - 10^{-8}	10^{-7}
Optical infrared	10^{-3} - 10^{-6}	10^{-4}
x-ray	10^{-8} - 10^{-10}	10^{-3}

In ecology, 35% of certified methods for determining pollution of the aquatic environment regulate the use of spectrum analyzers. In medicine, spectrophotometric analyzers make up 60% of the instrument stock of analytical medical laboratories; in scientific research in the field of chemistry, biology, medicine, pharmacology, 40% of the methods for analyzing substances are spectrophotometric methods of analysis [4].

The widespread use of spectral methods is explained by the comparative cheapness of spectrophotometric analyzers, as well as by the large number of developed analytical techniques. However, in most cases, spectrophotometric methods are designed to determine one component of the analyte, in this regard, practice, preliminary preparation of the analyzed sample is used with the purpose of separating other components interfering with the analysis, or special mathematical methods are used to process the results of spectrometric measurements. Currently, such methods are not sufficiently developed, and there is no preliminary processing in the means of converting the spectrometric signal, which limits the capabilities of computer tools for spectrometric analysis systems and information processing devices.

Atomic emission spectroscopy. Atomic emission spectral analysis - a method based on studying the spectrum of vapors of the test substance. The presence in the spectrum of characteristic lines inherent in the atoms of a given element indicates the presence of this element in the analyzed object (qualitative analysis).

The intensity of the lines in the spectra of elements serves as a measure of the concentration of the latter (quantitative analysis) [5]. When excited, atoms radiate energy, which can be fixed in the form of a spectrum of lines, and each element (for example, metal) has its own spectrum, inherent only to it. Thanks to this, it is possible to distinguish elements from each other, which is the basis of high-quality spectral analysis. Classification of methods of atomic spectroscopy is presented in Table. 2.

In practice, when using atomic emission spectral analysis, flame, electric arcs of direct and alternating current, low- and high-voltage condensed spark, low-voltage pulsed discharge, various forms of glow gas discharge, etc. are used as sources of excitation of spectra. also use different types of high-frequency discharges - a source of inductively coupled high-frequency plasma, microwave discharge, lasers, etc. [5].

Table 2. Classification of methods of atomic spectroscopy

Method	Radiation range	Process	Way of excitation
Atomic - emission	Optic	Photon emission	High temperature
Atomic - fluorescent	Optic	Photon emission	Electromagnetic radiation
Atomic absorption	Optic	Photon absorption	Not required
X-ray fluorescent	x-ray	Photon emission	Electromagnetic radiation (X-ray)

Atomic emission spectroscopy is widely used in environmental monitoring. Of all the methods for determining pollution of the aquatic environment, 15% of them regulate the use of atomic absorption analyzers, which determine the content of heavy metals in water - *Pb*, *Co*, *Hg*, *Vi*, etc. In the laboratories of the engineering industry, such spectrometers are used to determine the composition of structural metals, in the mining industry - to determine the composition of ore materials. The number of methods for analyzing materials using atomic emission spectroscopy reaches 30%. Modern atomic emission spectroscopy uses complex mathematical processing spectra in order to correct the background, determine the intensity of the lines of individual components, and calibrate instruments. The complexity of the software used in this case can be reduced by preprocessing the analytical signal, but the tools that implement such processing are currently insufficiently developed.

X-ray diffraction spectral analysis is used to determine the crystal structure of substances, as well as to determine their composition. It is used in geology and mineralogy in the study of rocks and minerals, in the mining industry in determining the composition of ore processing products, in the construction industry to determine the properties of building materials, in crystallography in the study of crystal lattices. The volume of production of X-ray diffraction analyzers is currently growing, its growth is about 15% per year [6].

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